

TECHNICAL REPORT

D6.2: Report 2 on measures to create innovation eco-system around ANGIE technology

Authors:

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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

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Approved by	All project partners
Keywords	Innovation; eco-system;

Abstract	This deliverable report presents the actions the consortium took to create an innovation eco-system around the ANGIE technology to foster its take-up in the clinical environments. Our goal is to create processes, involving all partners and stakeholders in the development of the technology from the start, and ensure that everyone feels as part of a large team, such as: a) creating a network of people with similar views and goals, b) increase the participation of diverse innovation stakeholders, c) build meaningful and prosperous relationships, d) hosting-attending industry/network events, and e) organizing technical workshops on implementation and operation of ANGIE and idea competitions.
Keywords	Innovation; eco-system;

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Creation / Change	Page
1.0	23/12/2022	Document approved by all Partners	All

PROJECT CONSORTIUM

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1. (Coordinator)	Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zürich	ETH	Switzerland
2.	University of Würzburg	UoW	Germany
3.	University of Barcelona	UoB	Spain
4.	University of Crete	UoC	Greece
5.	Stroke Alliance for Europe (SAFE)	SAFE	Pan-European
6.	Experian	EXP	Portugal
7.	Magnebotix	MGBX	Switzerland
8.	Discovery Foundation	DF	Greece
9.	Verhaert	VERT	Belgium

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable documents activities that are performed in Work Package (WP) 6 “Create an innovation eco-system around the ANGIE technology to foster its take-up in the clinical environments”. The WP6 objectives include:

- Mapping the existing innovation in localized targeted drug delivery across the EU
- Creating a network of people with similar views and goals
- Reaching out to European and Local Governments.
- Developing online courses on ANGIE technology.
- Organising technical workshops on implementation and operation of ANGIE.
- Organising idea competitions

The purpose of this document is to report the measures taken in creating an innovation ecosystem around the ANGIE technology.

1.1. Scope

The present document is the Deliverable 6.2 “D6.2”: Report 2 on measures to create an innovation eco-system around ANGIE technology” (henceforth referred to as D6.2.). The main objectives of “D6.2” is to report the actions the consortium took to create an innovation eco-system around the ANGIE technology to foster its take-up in the clinical environments. Our goal is to create processes, involving all partners and stakeholders in the development of the technology from the start, and ensure that everyone feels as part of a large team, such as:

- Creating a network of people with similar views and goals;
- Increase the participation of diverse innovation stakeholders;
- Build meaningful and prosperous relationships;
- Hosting-attending industry/network events;
- Organizing technical workshops on implementation and operation of ANGIE and idea competitions;

1.2. Audience

This document (D6.2) is available to the public and the European Commission.

2. CREATING A NETWORK OF PEOPLE WITH SIMILAR VIEWS AND GOALS

2.1 TECHNOLOGY AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP MEET-UP GROUPS

Using the information of the first report D6.1, we identified Meetup.com as the most effective service used to organize online groups that help persons to host in-person and online events for people having similar interests. Through this platform we connected with technology and entrepreneurship meetup groups in EU, with people who are working in related fields to our own, that offer a variety of networking opportunities, and attended online networking, educational and entrepreneurship events.

We created the Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Group (<https://www.meetup.com/nanotechnology-for-targeted-drug-delivery-meetup-group/>) which is now part of Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Network. Through our group’s page we disseminated all the ANGIE Innovation Ecosystem related events and we connected with the below technology and entrepreneurship meet-up groups:

Organizer

Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Group

Member

Impact Hub Lisbon - Events & Meetups

Munich Startup Founder 101

Health Technology Forum: Berlin

STEM 4 Health Warsaw

Meetup E-Santé & Health Tech

Health Hack Academy Stockholm

Designing Health

SingularityU Benelux

Health 2.0 Hamburg

Make Health

Healthcare Tech Solutions and Innovation Meetup

Healthcare Innovators Meetup Leipzig

Health Engineering Finland

London Healthcare Blockchain

The Future of Health & Life Science

Women networking in Healthcare (HBA Basel)

H2 Health Hub Stockholm Meetup

Berlin Biotech Journalists

Part of **Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Network**

Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Group

Brussels, Belgium

12 members · Public group

Organized by **Discovery Foundation**

One HealthTech Stockholm

Digital Health Frankfurt am Main (Rhein-Main-Neckar)...

Swiss Health Innovation Meetup

Startup Factory

Biomedical Engineering Group Twente

Medtec Meetups - Medical Technology and Innovation

STEM 4 Health & AgTech Milano

Startup-Sprechstunde // Pfizer Healthcare Hub Berlin

Artificial Intelligence for Medical Technology

Hacking Health Berlin

Paris Healthcare Innovation Meetup

STEM 4 Health Berlin

O2LAB - Open Innovation Lab

CMX Global Group

2.1.1 STEM 4 Health Berlin, Berlin, Germany, 5555 members

This meetup group aims to connect digital health startups, biotech startups, students, developers, technologists, scientists, biologists, bioinformaticians, data analysts, business intelligence analysts, designers, social media networkers, freelancers, established companies, institutes or organizations, venture capitalists, entrepreneurs, essentially anyone interested in life sciences, healthcare technologies and related businesses, with stakeholders in the healthcare system.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/STEM4health-Berlin/>

2.1.2 SingularityU Benelux, Eindhoven, Netherlands, 2.184 members

SingularityU Benelux provides educational programs and events to help the Benelux community understand cutting-edge technologies to positively impact billions of people. These technologies are Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Nanotechnology, Biotechnology, Neuroscience, Sensors, 3D printers and Energy & Environmental Systems.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/SingularityUBenelux/>

2.1.3. Paris Healthcare Innovation Meetup, Paris, France, 1463 members

This group is for anyone interested in health, e-health, innovation, education, training and those who want to come together to share ideas worth spreading. All types of public and speakers are welcome, doctors, health professionals, entrepreneurs, start-ups, medical laboratories, students and doctors to join their group to meet and discuss regularly.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/Paris-Healthcare-Innovation-Meetup/>

2.1.4. Hacking Health Berlin, Berlin, Germany, 1.281 members

Hacking Health is designed to improve healthcare by inviting technology creators and healthcare professionals to collaborate on realistic, human-centric solutions to front-line problems. They have partnered with organizations like the Berlin Institute of Health, Data Natives, EIT Health, Fraunhofer Venture and the German Ministry of Health to host and support hackathons in Germany and throughout Europe.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/Hacking-Health-Berlin/>

2.1.5. Artificial Intelligence for Medical Technology, Amsterdam, Netherlands, 1.136 members

The healthcare industry stands out from other industries in many ways. The potential value of data-driven applications is by far more evident than in any other industry, and the amounts and diversity of medical data is abundant. Yet, the pace of innovation is slow, which is unfortunate in the context of the rapid advancements in the fields of computing and artificial intelligence. This group's mission is to accelerate innovation in data-driven healthcare by bringing together healthcare professionals, data specialists, and general enthusiasts.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/Artificial-Intelligence-for-Medical-Technology/>

2.1.6. Startup-Sprechstunde // Pfizer Healthcare Hub Berlin, Berlin, Germany, 1205 members

The Pfizer Healthcare Hub organizes the "Start-up Consultation Hours" – open for startups and everyone else interested in the Digital Health sector in order to listen and ask questions related to a specific topic. Pfizer's experts give insights from the pharmaceutical industry and external experts explain complex topics. From very specific event topics like the "German Drug Advertising Act" to hot topics such as "IoT in Healthcare" – everyone is welcome to come, ask and connect with their team and other healthcare innovators and entrepreneurs during the subsequent networking.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/startup-sprechstunde/>

2.1.7. STEM 4 Health & AgTech Milano, Milano, Italy, 912 members

This meet-up group aims to connect digital health startups, biotech startups, students, developers, technologists, scientists, biologists, bioinformatics, data analysts, business intelligence analysts, designers, social media networkers, freelancers, established companies, institutes or organisations, venture capitalists, entrepreneurs, essentially anyone interested in life sciences, healthcare technologies and related business, with stakeholders in the healthcare system.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/STEM-4-Health-AgTech-Milano/>

2.1.8. Medtec Meetups - Medical Technology and Innovation, London, United Kingdom, 338 members

This group aims to understand and explore the challenges for medical technology developers, clinical researchers and start-up entrepreneurs surrounding: R&D, design, manufacturing processes, regulation to help you take a fresh look at your own projects. Medtec meetups will deliver educational insights on important IP and legal considerations, routes to secure the critical funding, setting up an effective distribution system and the best strategies for international expansion.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/MEDTEC-Meetups/>

2.1.9. Biomedical Engineering Group Twente, Enschede, Netherlands, 128 members

Biomedical Engineering Group Twente is a scientific community, which refers to students, researchers, and professionals interested to contribute to biomedical engineering research and development. Their events enable knowledge sharing and promote updates of future research directions, as well as connection and networking with colleagues.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/BioEngTwente/>

2.1.10. Designing Health, London, United Kingdom, 767 members

Designing Health wants to connect everyone interested in designing and delivering services, products and initiatives to improve health. They find that designing for health can be challenging and want to create a space where designers, healthcare professionals, and health enthusiasts can exchange knowledge and support each other.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/designing-health/>

2.1.11. Healthcare Tech Solutions and Innovation Meetup, London, United Kingdom, 169 members

This meetup group showcases the latest in Healthcare Innovation bringing together thought leadership and industry expertise. Their events enable inspiration in solving a range of healthcare problems and sharing the latest technology innovations in healthcare.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/London-Healthcare-Innovative-IT-Solutions-Meetup-Group/>

2.1.12. Women networking in Healthcare, Basel, Switzerland, 602 members

Women networking in Healthcare group, provides educational opportunities to develop cutting-edge industry knowledge and leadership skills and recognizes outstanding women in the industry. This online group is open to all interested parties, including women and men, who wish to network and learn from professionals involved in all aspects of the healthcare industry, including manufacturers, clinicians, researchers, marketers, educators and communicators. The group provides women in pharmaceutical, biotech, and related healthcare professions the opportunity to network across many countries on the European continent.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/HBA-Basel/>

2.1.13. Health 2.0 Hamburg, Germany, 593 members

Health 2.0 Hamburg is a network focused on innovations in the delivery of healthcare and health related technology. Members are entrepreneurial minded founders of a digital health startup, innovation directors from health care corporations, Big Data and eHealth Decision Makers from insurances, pharmaceutical

companies, med tech companies, university hospitals, clinics, healthcare professionals - and of course patients who embrace technology assisted solutions to manage their disease.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/Health20Hamburg/>

2.1.14. The Future of Health & Life Science, Berlin, Germany, 542 members

This meetup group focus on healthcare and life sciences. The group's members are start uppers, investors, developers and freelancers, interested in healthcare and life sciences.

Meetup link: https://www.meetup.com/health_and_life_science/

2.1.15. Health Hack Academy Stockholm, Sweden, 588 members

Health Hack Academy is more than a hackathon. Health Hack Academy is an innovation program taking you from problem (challenge) through ideas and prototyping to business concept. Health Hack Academy is the collaborative space where awesome projects are developed aimed at solving real life health issues, be it in health care, self-care or wellbeing.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/health-hack-academy-stockholm/>

2.1.16. Health Hub Stockholm Meetup, Stockholm, Sweden, 723 members

A meetup group that aims to drive tomorrow's healthcare. This is the place where entrepreneurs, decision makers, healthcare professionals and industry leaders meet, share and discuss the possibilities with digital health.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/h2-health-hub-stockholm-meetup/>

2.1.17. Meetup E-Santé & Health Tech, Paris, France, 463 members

A meetup group focused on Health technology, and innovation in the medical field. Health professionals, doctors, nurses, developers, startups, thinkers are welcome to join different events dedicated healthcare innovation.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/meetup-e-sante-health-tech/>

2.1.18. STEM 4 Health Warsaw, Poland, 221 members

This meetup group aims to connect digital health startups, biotech startups, students, developers, technologists, scientists, biologists, bioinformaticians, data analysts, artificial intelligence and genomics experts, business intelligence analysts, designers, social media networkers, freelancers, established companies, institutes or organizations, venture capitalists, entrepreneurs, essentially anyone interested in life sciences, healthcare technologies and related businesses, with stakeholders in the healthcare system.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/stem-4-health-warsaw/>

2.1.19. Health Technology Forum: Berlin, Germany, 260 members

Health Technology Forum (HTF) is a platform for people worldwide who have a common interest in making healthcare better, more accessible and affordable. Their international network of technology and

healthcare entrepreneurs, developers, regulators, and providers are advancing the pace of healthcare innovation by engaging in exciting and productive dialogue between experts in healthcare. At their meetups they discuss real-life technology use-cases from hospitals, doctor offices, medical billing, insurance, remote monitoring, pharmaceuticals, health-and-wellness, and various patient-care services.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/healthtechnologyforum-berlin/>

2.1.20. Munich Startup Founder 101, Munich, Germany, 6,772 members

Startup Founder 101 brings together aspiring and experienced tech entrepreneurs to discuss, meet, and collaborate to build great new startups, and to push the startup ecosystem forward.

This group hosts numerous free events throughout the year where you can learn the best practices of starting a company from people who have been there and done that. The group gives you the opportunity to meet local founders and investors, exchange ideas with experts, get feedback on your idea, participate in startup workshops, and more.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/munich-startup-founder-101/>

2.1.21. Startup Factory, Brussels, Belgium, 4,246 members

The Startup Factory group is here to give entrepreneurship a boost. An entrepreneurship community to enable entrepreneurs, talented young graduates and experienced executives to more effectively find, engage and support each other, work together and thrive locally, regionally and internationally. This is a group for anyone interested in entrepreneurship, to help entrepreneurial members achieve their objectives and realize their aspirations.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/startup-factory/>

2.1.22. Impact Hub Lisbon - Events & Meetups, Lisbon, Portugal, 3,101 members

A global community of Impact Makers, Events & Meetups are organized or co-organized by the Impact Hub Lisbon team, and embrace various topics such as: social businesses, social entrepreneurship, investment (social investment; patient capital; crowdfunding; fundraising; etc), circular economy, sharing economy and community building.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/impacthulibson/>

2.2. ANGIE ZENODO COMMUNITY

In addition to our activities in Meetup, we created the ANGIE Zenodo Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/angie-h2020eu/>). Built and developed by researchers, Zenodo is an online repository for EU-funded research that promotes Open Data and Science with more of 10,000 communities for researchers, medicals and public persons. The ANGIE Zenodo Community gathers all public deliverables, scientific publications and publicly available results of the project under one place. All the documents included in the Zenodo Community are under open access status and are freely available. All dissemination material produced for the project are already available, including newsletters. The ANGIE Zenodo Community is being continuously updated with new publicly available content on targeted drug delivery and research results on microrobots targeting the brain.

ANGIE - MAgnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the tarGeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body

Recent uploads

February 3, 2022 (v1)
Journal article
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Magnetically Assisted Robotic Fetal Surgery for the Treatment of Spina Bifida

Simone Gervasoni; Jonas Lussi; Silvia Viviani; Quentin Boehler; Nicole Ochsenbein; Ueli Moehrlen; Bradley J. Nelson;

Spina bifida is a congenital defect that occurs on the vertebral spine of a fetus. The most severe form causes exposure of the spinal cord and spinal nerve and has important repercussions on the life of the newborn child. Current prenatal operative procedures require laparotomy of the abdomen as well

Uploaded on December 22, 2022

Published in IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics.

October 7, 2021 (v1)
Journal article
Open Access
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Powering and Fabrication of Small-Scale Robotics Systems

Salvador Pané; Pedro Wendel-Garcia; Yonca Belce; Xiang-Zhong Chen; Josep Puigmartí-Luis;

Purpose of Review: The increasing number of contributions in the field of small-scale robotics is significantly associated with the progress in material science and process engineering during the last half century. With the objective of integrating the most optimal materials for the propulsion of these

Uploaded on December 22, 2022

Published in NANOROBOTICS AND MICROROBOTICS.

May 25, 2022 (v1)
Journal article
Open Access
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Toward More Inclusive Networks and Initiatives in Innovation Ecosystems: Protocol for a Systematic Review

Georgia Ntina; Eirini Mavromanolaki; Andreas D Flouris;

Expanding the cooperation and enlarging the participation of more diverse stakeholders within innovation ecosystems will increase their efficiency and capacity to contribute at local, regional, and national levels. This paper presents the protocol for a systematic review that will identify &id

Uploaded on December 22, 2022

Published in JMIR Research Protocols.

September 27, 2021 (v1)
Conference paper
Open Access
View

Magnetic small-scale robots: Principles, applications and challenges

S. Pané; J. Puigmartí; M. Pinto; E. Mavromanolaki; A. D. Flouris; T. S. Mayor; T. C. Lüthmann; D. Sargent; B. J. Nelson;

Last two decades has seen a growth of the research on untethered mobile small-scale robots. These motile devices display the ability to travel through fluids by transforming the energy generated by an external power source into mechanical motion. As a result, these devices are being recognized as pr

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New upload

Community

the future of drug delivery

ANGIE - MAgnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the tarGeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body

This repository community collects research outputs related to the ANGIE project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952152

MAgnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the tarGeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body – ANGIE - aims to develop a novel, minimally invasive approach for treatment of strokes.

Most strokes occur when a blood vessel in the brain is occluded by a clot. This clot then prevents areas in the brain from being supplied with oxygen, resulting in the sudden death of brain tissue. Strokes are a leading cause of death and disability worldwide, and stroke cases are expected to rise in the coming years. The most common treatment for this kind of stroke involves injecting a thrombolytic drug (usually rtPA) into the blood, which then dissolves the clot. Tiny mobile magnetic devices are showing huge potential for future biomedical applications. The EU-funded ANGIE project will forge ahead with small-scale robotics, magnetic navigation systems and localised targeted drug delivery. Specifically, the project will develop magnetically steerable wireless nanodevices for the targeted delivery of therapeutic agents via the body's vascular system. By creating a baseline of knowledge and skills for localised targeted drug delivery, the project will increase health professionals' capacity to treat multiple chronic diseases. Moreover, it will enable doctors to deliver drugs precisely where needed with minimal side effects.

2.3. INCREASING THE PARTICIPATION OF DIVERSE INNOVATION STAKEHOLDERS

A challenge that we have faced so far was to find ways to “open-up” our innovation ecosystem and to increase the participation of diverse innovation stakeholders, particularly from low-innovation countries and particularly during the phase that we are now – the ecosystem formation period. Therefore, we are working towards a systematic review of the literature to identify these best practices. Our systematic review protocol has been designed according to the highest quality guidelines developed by the Cochrane Library, it has been registered in the Open Science Foundation registry, and was published in the JMIR Research Protocols journal:

- Ntina G, Mavromanolaki E, Flouris AD. (2022). Toward more inclusive networks and initiatives in innovation ecosystems: protocol for a systematic review. JMIR Res Protoc; 11(5):e34071. doi: 10.2196/34071.

2.4 BUILDING MEANINGFUL AND PROSPEROUS RELATIONSHIPS WITH STAKEHOLDERS

Using the information of the first report D6.1, where we identified researchers, start-ups, entrepreneurship organizations, policy makers, journalists and news outlets we created an email list¹ and we shared our newsletter to communicate the project's scope and deliver our latest news, actions and results in order to foster connection and collaboration with leading actors in the targeted drug delivery area.

3. HOSTING AND ATTENDING INDUSTRY/NETWORK EVENTS

3.1. ANGIE SATELLITE SYMPOSIUM 2021

We organized a satellite symposium during the 2021 Bionanotox conference to showcase our work up to that point as well as our plans for the future. The main topic of Bionanotox Conference is Bio Nanotoxicology that lies on the interface of several scientific fields, such as biology, chemistry, toxicology, computational science chemistry, nanotechnology and biotechnology. The Conference is a continuation of a long-term co-operation between scientists of these fields, which has been ongoing for the last 20 years, in the frame of the bilateral scientific state programs. Scientists working in the most prominent Universities, Technological Institutes and Companies as well as distinguished field specialists coming from several countries attended this Conference. The proceedings from this symposium have been included in a journal supplement published in Public Health Toxicology.

¹ ANNEX I

CHAIRS: Andreas D. Flouris, Georgia Mita	
16.30-17.00	<p>AD1</p> <p>MAGNETIC SMALL-SCALE ROBOTS: PRINCIPLES, APPLICATIONS AND CHALLENGES</p> <p>S. Papp¹, J. Pulgarin^{2,3}, M. Pinar⁴, A. Navarro⁵, E. Marmontani⁶, A. D. Flouris^{7,8}, T. S. Moore⁹, T. C. Liberman¹⁰, D. Sengupta¹¹, R. J. Nelson¹²</p> <p>¹ Multi Scale Robotics Lab, ETH Zurich, Switzerland, Zurich, CH-8092 Switzerland</p> <p>² Departamento de Ciencia de Materiales I Química Física, Institut de Química Tècnica i Computacional, BarCELONA, 08035 Spain</p> <p>³ ICREA, Pg. Lluís Companys 23, Barcelona, 08010 Spain</p> <p>⁴ ESTERMAN, Portugal</p> <p>⁵ Discovery Foundation, PERU, Greece</p> <p>⁶ FAME Laboratory, University of Thessaly, 42100, Greece</p> <p>⁷ SATECH, Transport Phenomena Research Centre, FEUP, Portugal</p> <p>⁸ Institute of Pharmacy and Food Chemistry, Julius-Maximilians-University Würzburg, Am Hubland, Würzburg, 97074 Germany</p> <p>⁹ Agapostolis AG, Röhrenstr. 14, 8932 Schönen</p>
17.00-17.15	<p>AD2</p> <p>SOFT-HARD MAGNETICALLY DRIVEN MICROBROBOTIC DEVICES</p> <p>E. Mentes¹, C.J. Akantaris², J. Pulgarin^{3,4}, R. J. Nelson⁵, S. Papp⁶</p> <p>¹ Multi Scale Robotics Lab, ETH Zurich, Switzerland, Zurich, CH-8092 Switzerland</p> <p>² Departamento de Ciencia de Materiales I Química Física, Institut de Química Tècnica i Computacional, BarCELONA, 08035 Spain</p> <p>³ ICREA, Pg. Lluís Companys 23, Barcelona, 08010 Spain</p>
17.15-17.30	<p>AD3</p> <p>MARRIYING INORGANICS AND BIOLOGICS - OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES</p> <p>K. Richter¹, M. Richter², F. Lendner³, S. Papp⁴, T. Liberman⁵</p> <p>¹ Institute of Pharmacy and Food Chemistry, Julius-Maximilians-University Würzburg, Am Hubland, Würzburg, 97074 Germany</p> <p>² Multi Scale Robotics Lab, ETH Zurich, Switzerland, Zurich, CH-8092 Switzerland</p>
17.30-18.00	<p>AD4</p> <p>MICROFLUIDIC TECHNOLOGIES FOR CHEMISTRY, MATERIALS SCIENCE AND BIOTECHNOLOGY</p> <p>J. Pulgarin^{1,2}</p> <p>¹ Departamento de Ciencia de Materiales I Química Física, Institut de Química Tècnica i Computacional, 08035 Barcelona, Spain</p> <p>² ICREA, Pg. Lluís Companys 23, 08010 Barcelona, Spain</p>
18.00-18.15	<p>AD5</p> <p>IN FLOW CONTROLLED SYNTHESIS OF BLOOD CLOTS</p> <p>K. S. Herrera Restrepo¹, A. Martínez-Buñil², A. D. Flouris^{3,4}, M. Pinar⁵, A. Navarro⁶, E. Marmontani⁷, T. S. Moore⁸, S. Papp⁹, J. Iguez¹⁰, J. Pulgarin^{11,12}</p> <p>¹ Departamento de Ciencia de Materiales I Química Física, Institut de Química Tècnica i Computacional, 08035 Barcelona, Spain</p> <p>² FAME Laboratory, University of Thessaly, Greece</p> <p>³ Discovery Foundation, PERU, Greece</p> <p>⁴ ESTERMAN, Portugal</p> <p>⁵ SATECH Laboratory, Transport Phenomena Research Centre, Engineering Faculty of Porto University, 4200-465 Porto, Portugal</p> <p>⁶ Institute of Robotics and Intelligent Systems, ETH Zurich, Switzerland, Zurich, CH-8092 Zurich, Switzerland</p> <p>⁷ ICREA, Pg. Lluís Companys 23, 08010 Barcelona, Spain</p>

18.15-18.30	<p>AD6</p> <p>EVOLUTION, GAPS, AND TRENDS IN THE ORIGINS OF INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS</p> <p>E. Marmontani¹, G. Mita², S. Karalatz³, A. Sotiriou⁴, M. Pinar⁵, A. Navarro⁶, T. S. Moore⁷, J. Pulgarin^{8,9}, A. D. Flouris¹⁰</p> <p>¹ Discovery Foundation, Greece</p> <p>² ESTERMAN, Portugal</p> <p>³ Multi Scale Robotics Lab, ETH Zurich, Switzerland</p> <p>⁴ SATECH, Transport Phenomena Research Centre, FEUP, Portugal</p> <p>⁵ Departamento de Ciencia de Materiales I Química Física, Institut de Química Tècnica i Computacional, BarCELONA, Spain</p> <p>⁶ ICREA, Barcelona, Spain</p> <p>⁷ FAME Laboratory, University of Thessaly, Greece</p>				
<table border="0"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Congress Secretariat</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Scientific Information</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Albina Gegej Tel: +30 210 7493009 E-mail: inform@conanetox.org</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Shahman M.I. – shahman@yandex.ru Tatsuki A.M. – aris@med.uoc.gr</td> </tr> </table>		Congress Secretariat	Scientific Information	Albina Gegej Tel: +30 210 7493009 E-mail: inform@conanetox.org	Shahman M.I. – shahman@yandex.ru Tatsuki A.M. – aris@med.uoc.gr
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3.2 ANGIE SATELLITE SYMPOSIUM 2022

In October 2022, we were planning to host the second ANGIE symposium during the 2022 Bionanotox conference, but unfortunately the conference was cancelled due to the difficulties resulting from the war in Ukraine.

3.3. JAPANESE-EUROPEAN WORKSHOP ON AI

Through our activities aimed at creating a sustainable ecosystem, the ANGIE consortium was invited to attend the Japanese-European Workshop on Moonshot program goal 3 “Co-evolving AI and Robots towards 2050” which took place in Switzerland from September 21 to 23, 2022. A delegation from Japan consisting of 25 researchers attended the event in order to seek potential collaboration partners from Europe. The delegation was accompanied by representatives from the Japan Science and Technology Agency JST and the Science & Technology Office Tokyo (STO), Embassy of Switzerland in Japan. The Moonshot Research and Development Program promotes high-risk, high-impact R&D based on ambitious and inspiring ideas to achieve disruptive innovation and radical solutions for social issues by 2050.

3.4. TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY FOR CARDIOVASCULAR AND CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASES MEETUP EVENT

In December 2022, we organized the Meetup event “Targeted Drug delivery for Cardiovascular and Cerebrovascular Diseases”. This online ANGLE Meetup event brought together medical experts in cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases with the ambition to generate new research collaborations and future applications. The meetup event provided medical doctors, engineers, scientists, new researchers and stakeholders from different disciplines with a unique and exciting format to learn the most current information about nano-carriers in the diagnosis and treatment of cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases. The event was the perfect platform to share, experience, foster collaborations across health care, pharmaceutical, biotech & diagnostic industries with hospitals and academia. The event flyer and screenshots taken during the presentations are presented below.

TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY FOR CARDIOVASCULAR AND CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASES
MEETUP EVENT

Our Awesome Speakers: www.h2020-angie.eu

Dr. Kostas Tsarouhas, MD, MSc, PhD, ERT Consultant of Cardiology University General Hospital of Larissa, Larissa, Greece
“*Atherosclerosis and coronary artery disease, thrombosis mechanisms and vulnerable atheromatic plaque*”

Dr. Michael Kiparakis, MD, Surgeon, University General Hospital of Heraklion in Greece
“*Coronary Disease and CABG*”

Dr Vasileios Siokas, MD, MSc, PhD, Laboratory of Neurogenetics, Department of Neurology, University Hospital of Larissa, Faculty of Medicine, School of Health Sciences, University of Thessaly, Larissa, Greece
“*Future therapeutic options of transcranial magnetic stimulation in Neurology*”

Dr. Georgios Z. Papadakis, MD, MPH, PhD, Principal Researcher Hybrid Molecular Imaging Unit (HMU), Computational Biomedicine Laboratory (CBML), Foundation for Research & Technology Hellas (FORTH), Heraklion, Crete, Greece
“*Current status and future prospects of PET-imaging applications in the management of patients with Gastro-Entero-Pancreatic Neuroendocrine tumors*”

FOLLOW THE LINK BELOW TO JOIN VIA ZOOM
<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/93818358088?pwd=ckMlMkZlR2ZDZDeWZaeTRBUjU9>

15 DECEMBER 2022
14:00 CET

Supported by the European Union
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FORTH Institute of Computer Science
NIH
HMU

TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY FOR CARDIOVASCULAR AND CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASES
MEETUP EVENT

"Current status and future prospects of PET-imaging applications in the management of patients with Gastro-Entero-Pancreatic Neuroendocrine tumors"

A narrowing of the coronary arteries that prevents adequate blood supply to the heart muscle.

Normal Artery **Narrowing of Artery**

Abnormal accumulation of lipid or fatty substances or fatty atherosclerotic in the lumen of coronary artery.

It may progress to the point where the heart muscle is damaged due to lack of

Interaction of WS & SS in favoring plaque rupture

A **B**

Lower ESS **High ESS**

Low shear stress **High shear stress**

Cap weakening **Cap thinning**

Pressure **Pressure**

4. ORGANIZING TECHNICAL WORKSHOPS ON IMPLEMENTATION AND OPERATION OF ANGLE AND IDEA COMPETITIONS

We developed a concept with two subsequent open innovation programmes to strengthen links between universities, industry and the start-up community, leading to greater research translation and commercialisation.

The ANGLE Kickstart programme, running from October 2022 until May 2023, invited students, researchers, clinicians, and other healthcare professionals (medical devices industry, pharmaceutical companies, etc.) to define a project/venture for developing an application” on the ANGLE “platform. In combination with a series of workshops, mentoring, and support from the centers of entrepreneurship of the consortium partners, this program effectively creates a network of individuals who share similar perspectives and values with respect to targeted drug delivery. After the completion of the program, promising projects will be selected in an open competition to participate in the subsequent program.

The ANGIE Acceleration programme, will run from the fall of 2023 to the spring of 2024, will support teams, that have successfully completed the kick-start program, and will be selected to continue to validate the business viability and technological feasibility of the concept. During the course of the programme, workshops will be conducted on topics related to technical, business, and financial aspects. Moreover, participating teams will have access to R&D facilities and subject matter experts as well as dedicated mentoring.

4.1 ANGIE KICKSTART PROGRAMME

The ANGIE Kick-start Programme, an initiative from the ANGIE project, is open for students, researchers, and healthcare professionals with an interest for targeted drug delivery. It starts with an idea for a targeted drug delivery intervention for treatment of a certain health condition and finishes with a definition of the concept, a viable business case and a prototype development plan.

The programme provides participants with mentored experiences in healthcare innovation through a combination of workshop activities, focused project work, and other appropriate professional development and networking opportunities. The programme draws on the many facets of the activities established in the ANGIE project, as well as the network of our academia and industry partners and external stakeholders.

The programme and its various activities is running from October 2022 until May 2023. During this period, participants work on their concepts under the supervision of their mentors. Expert-mentors from the participating organizations meet with the teams to provide guidance and feedback once a month.

Kick-start participants will benefit from a collaborative, open innovation process and access to a community of like-minded researchers, entrepreneurs and innovators.

We embedded a web-page in our website (www.h2020-angie.eu/innovation-ecosystem) where candidates could find all the relevant information about the Programme and the registration form as well.

The Angie Kick-start was promoted through our website (www.h2020-angie.eu), Twitter (www.twitter.com/angie_h2020) and LinkedIn account (www.linkedin.com/company/angie-h2020/). In addition, all partners contributed for the promotion of the Programme and shared the ANGIO kick-start brochure² through their network, websites and social media.

In October 2022, we held an online informative webinar session on the ANGIO kick-start Programme. Participants learned about the ANGIO project and its approach to targeted drug delivery. Moreover, we explained what the kick-start programme is and how we can support them to get started with the ANGIO technology platform.

Agenda

Thank you for joining us today!

- Welcome and introductions
- Overview of the ANGIO Kick-start Programme, **Gina Ntina**, Discovery Foundation
- The state of the technology and its applications, **Fabian Landers**, ETH Zürich
- The importance of stroke research in saving lives and reducing disability after stroke, **Arlene Wilkie**, SAFE
- Practical information of the ANGIO kick-start Programme, **Benoit De Vrieze**, VERHAERT Masters in Innovation
- Meet the other participants**. Take the opportunity to introduce yourself and share your interest in targeted drug delivery therapies.
- Q&A
- Wrap up

Frequently asked questions

Can I work on any idea?
You can participate with any targeted drug delivery idea based on your interest and expertise.

Working alone or in a team?
We advise to work in a team of 2-3 people with different backgrounds

What will happen to the results of our work?
Your idea and project remain yours. We only require you to pitch it at the final bootcamp.

ANGIE Innovation Ecosystem

The ANGIO innovation ecosystem brings together health professionals, researchers, entrepreneurs and manufacturers providing them with online courses and technical workshops to understand the innovation aspects of the new technology and giving them examples of applications in different fields.

We create new market opportunities for entrepreneurs, companies and investors.

Project Overview – The Concept of ANGIO

Small-Scale Robots and Magnetic Navigation Systems

Helical Magnetic Microrobot for in vitro drug delivery

Magnetic Navigation System for cardiac ablation with magnetically steerable catheters

Currently, the ANGIO kick-start Programme candidates have been assigned to their teams and participated to the first workshop “Discovering the clinical journey” where we helped them understand the current clinical journey for the health condition or disease they have chosen to focus on. This workshop provided them with the entire sequence of events that a patient experiences within a given healthcare system or across providers, from scheduling an appointment for a regular check-up to receiving treatment for a certain disease. Participants designed a personalized patient journey map of the medical condition they are focusing on, which was a useful strategy to employ during the development of their targeted drug delivery treatment.

In addition, they have been provided with personalized mentoring sessions on technical and innovation aspects. Expert-mentors within our consortium guide them through the development of their projects, connect them with a broader network and increase their entrepreneurship engagement.

² ANNEX II

Future actions

The ANGIE kick-start Programme will continue with more workshops to introduce participants to the ANGIE technology platform and how it can be used to develop new targeted drug delivery therapies. In addition, our innovation experts will help them to design a viable business model for the health condition they have chosen to focus on and the targeted drug delivery therapy they envision. Finally, in May 2023, we will organize the final bootcamp of the ANGIE Kick-start Programme, where all participants will be able to present their idea for a new targeted drug delivery therapy to the other participants, the consortium partners and selected invitees. All participants will receive individual feedback and tailored advice to define a research project and to check the technical and clinical feasibility of their idea. The most promising projects will be invited to participate in the ANGIE Acceleration Programme that will run from the fall of 2023 to the spring of 2024 and will provide further support.

Annex I

ORGANIZATION	ORGANIZATION
KSA KANTONSSPITAL AARAU, SWITZERLAND	POPULATION HEALTH RESEARCH INSTITUTE, ONTARIO CANADA
CENTRE FOR RESEARCH IN MEDICAL DEVICES, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND	NANOFLEX ROBOTICS
FUNDACIO ICTUS	CONSULTORIA E APLICAÇÕES EM SISTEMAS E TECNOLOGIA, LDA
DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS, UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	DEPARTMENT OF NEUROSCIENCES, KU LEUVEN
DEPARTMENT OF NEUROSCIENCES AND MENTAL HEALTH, HOSPITAL SANTA MARIA, UNIVERSITY OF LISBON	ORTHOROBOTICS
ESO	BIO INNOVATION INSTITUTE
SCHOOL OF MEDICINE, LILLE UNIVERSITY	IWA CONSULTING
CONSULTORIA E APLICAÇÕES EM SISTEMAS E TECNOLOGIA, LDA	WORLD STROKE ORGANISATION
CATALAN HEALTH SERVICE	WELLINGTON PARTNERS
BIOMEDPARTNERS	KULJETINPROTEIINI-VÄLITTEINEN LÄÄKEAINEIDEN KOHDENTAMINEN, TRANSPORTER GROUP
DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING, IMPERIAL UK	TECHSTARS
TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY WITH NANOMEDICINE, UNIVERSITY OF GRONINGEN	TECHILL
TECHTOUR	INNOVATION FOR HEALTH 2023
PARIS REGION HEALTH CARE INNOVATION	ATHENS HACHING HEALTH
HELLENIC ALLICANCE FOR STROKE	STARTUPREPORTER
EU-STARTUPS	INSIGHT
EUROPEAN PROJECTS ASSOCIATION	ETN MAGAZINE
CARDIOLOGY UNIVERSITY, GENERAL HOSPITAL OF LARISSA, GREECE	LABORATORY OF NEUROGENETICS, DEPARTMENT OF NEUROLOGY, UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL OF LARISSA, GREECE
UNIVERSITY GENERAL, HOSPITAL OF HERAKLION, GREECE	BAWA BIOTECH LLC
EMPA, PARTICLES-BIOLOGY INTERACTIONS LAB	BIOPHARMACEUTICALS, UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA
BIOPHARMACEUTICALS SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA	DEPARTMENT OF POLITICAL AND SOCIAL SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY OF FLORENCE

DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION SCIENCES, WEST UNIVERSITY OF TIMIȘOARA	PHARMACOECONOMICS AND OUTCOMES RESEARCH IBERIA
DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACY, PHARMACOLOGY AND HEALTH TECHNOLOGIES, UNIVERSITY OF LISBON	NUFFIELD COUNCIL ON BIOETHICS, KING'S COLLEGE LONDON
NATIONAL EHEALTH LIVING LAB, NETHERLANDS	CATALAN HEALTH SERVICE
DEPARTMENT OF ECONOMICS AND LAW, UNIVERSITY OF MACERATA	DEPARTMENT OF MEDICINE AND PSYCHOLOGY, SAPIENZA UNIVERSITY
EUROPEAN ALLIANCE OF ASSOCIATIONS FOR RHEUMATOLOGY	DEPARTMENT FOR HEALTH EVIDENCE, Radboud University Nijmegen Medical Centre
DEPARTMENT OF CLINICAL EPIDEMIOLOGY AND MEDICAL TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT (KEMTA), MAASTRICHT UNIVERSITY MEDICAL CENTRE	HEALTH TECHNOLOGY AND SERVICES RESEARCH DEPARTMENT, TECHNICAL MEDICAL CENTRE, UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE
NEUROLOGY DEPARTMENT, AZIENDA OSPEDALIERA SANT'ANNA HOSPITAL	DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH POLICY, LONDON SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS

ANGIE kick-start Programme

The ANGIE Kick-start Programme is an initiative from the ANGIE project that aims to create a solid baseline of knowledge and skills for localised targeted drug delivery based on steerable wireless nanodevices, capable of navigating the body vascular system to deliver drugs where no other instrument can go.

In the ANGIE Kick-start Programme you start with an idea related to targeted drug delivery to treat a certain health condition and you finish with a clear definition of the concept, a viable business case and a prototype development plan.

Raising awareness and triggering entrepreneurship for targeted drug delivery.

Contact us

www.h2020-angie.eu
info@h2020-angie.eu

Kick-start programme benefits

- Team support to refine your idea: Our mentors will step you through the process of turning your idea to a viable project.
- A series of workshops:
 - 24 November 2022 - Discovering the clinical journey
 - 8 December 2022 - Understanding Healthcare Systems
 - 16 February 2023 - Creating new targeted drug delivery applications
 - 16 March 2023 - Designing a viable business model
- Mentorship: You will be mentored by an experienced venture builder to provide guidance and feedback once a month.
- Build your network: You will build key contacts in your sector including researchers, companies, universities and funding.

Develop your skill set with our free workshops that target your professional objectives, fill gaps in knowledge and expertise, and enable you to turn your learnings into action for real-time impact

Join the ANGIE kick-start Programme

Fill in the registration form on our website: www.h2020-angie.eu

Registration starts 1 September 2022
 Registration ends: 20 October 2022

The programme and its various activities will run from October 2022 until the May 2023.

Programme Outline

- Team formation
- A series of workshops on targeted drug delivery topics to help the teams develop their idea.
- A final bootcamp where the teams present their project and the best projects are selected.
- Support in project definition and opportunities around every corner for getting new funding, boosting growth and igniting business.

Find us on

